

IJMSBR

<https://www.ijmsbr.com/>

Impact Factor: 6.049

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.

The Impact of Bureaucracy Problems on Investment Opportunities "The Case of Jordan"

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾**Eid Abass Al-rafia**

Maan College, Al-Balqa Applied University, Jordan Business and Finance Department

⁽²⁾**Mohammad Raja Salah**

Maan College, Al-Balqa Applied University, Jordan Business and Finance Department

* **E-mail of corresponding author: mohd_alsalah@bau.edu.jo**

Abstract

The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of bureaucracy problems on investment opportunities. A well-structured five Likert's scale questionnaire is used to collect data from a targeted population of 280 respondents. Data collected is used to give clear answers to whether bureaucracy problems have impact on investment opportunities or not. Statistical package No 16 is used to generate analysis. Various kinds of statistics were included such as tables, means and standard deviations, coefficients and so on. Results have confirmed that these problems have strong negative impact on investment opportunities in Jordan, therefore the null hypothesis are rejected. Given the significant strong negative relationship between bureaucracy problems and investment opportunities, it is practically necessary to continuously improve public operational systems and avoid the adoption of excessive bureaucratic systems. Flexible systems and Easier and simpler procedures can be reinforced to weaken the impact of these obstacles on investment opportunities.

Keywords: Bureaucratic systems, Bureaucratic problems, Investment opportunities. Jordan

1. INTRODUCTION

Bureaucracy is common system practiced in most countries all over the world. In general, economic development. Sustainability refers to a system in which certain individuals "mostly referred to as officials" are given the task of making decisions instead of others. Swanson (2017) argued that professional authorized bodies do not normally take decisions. The system of bureaucracy exists in both publically and privately owned organizations. The normal structure of such organizations is made of many policymaking divisions, units or departments. Policies made under the phenomena of excessive bureaucracy tend to have great consequences on other parties such as customers, clients and existing or potential investors. Investment attraction is among the most important objectives of government policies and strategies. Investment hesitation can be explained as follows: in one hand, investor's desire to invest are affected by a list of factors such as political, social, geographical, economic, cultural and legislative factors. In the other hand investment decision is highly hindered by obstructive, excessive and extreme bureaucracy. As a result, serious attempts should be made to overcome the obstacles associated with the rigidity and complexity of bureaucracy. According to Swanson (2017) business and government environments are continuously changing and bureaucracy in general hinders effective solutions. Most governments strive for more economic development. Sustainability and the reduction of unemployment can be achieved through the attraction of foreign investment and the accumulation of local investment. According to (Mohammed et al.,2013) the presence of bureaucracy negatively affects economic development and sustainability. The

notion of obstructive bureaucracy is undermined and to some extent is neglected in empirical and practical research papers. Therefore, the purpose of this research paper is to critically evaluate the bureaucratic inner problems. The proposed evaluation concentrates on the following twelve problems: slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employee's potential and capabilities.

2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Direct and indirect investment is considered as top priority for most governments across the world. The government of Jordan has worked very hard to provide investment friendly atmosphere through modern investment laws, tax allowances and industrial zones. Unfortunately, the presence of many levels bureaucratic structures as found in most government departments still forms the most pressing challenge in attracting foreign investment and expanding local investment. This statement is in line with the findings of (Chipea & Banciu 2013). In order to overcome the above problem and at the same time meets investor's needs, many levels bureaucratic structures are no longer suitable for modern organizations. Hamel (2012) pointed that traditional rigid bureaucratic system is no longer suitable for modern organizations that strongly adopts to change and uses innovative management practices. Global and modern investors require management structures that are compatible to their systems and their objectives. In this instance private sector, bureaucracy could be an alternative to public sector bureaucracy, because private sector organizations have flexible structures and have encourages creativity in the work place. This fact is highly stressed in the findings of Steiber (2014). The acknowledgement of this fact could be the solution for the long lasting Jordanian bureaucracy. Accordingly, comprehensive evaluation of the possible impact of bureaucracy problems on investment opportunities "the case of investment potentials in Jordan" is required.

3. PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The study aimed to evaluate implications of bureaucracy problems on investment opportunities "the case of investment potentials in Jordan". A comprehensive and practical approach will be used to determine the impact of all listed problems so that, investors and government officials can see what hinders investment opportunities in Jordan.

4. OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

The objectives of this study are as follows:

1. Evaluate the possible impact of slower or delay in decision making on Investment Opportunities.
2. Evaluate the possible impact of centralized lengthy procedures on Investment Opportunities.
3. Evaluate the possible impact of lack of transparency on Investment Opportunities.
4. Evaluate the possible impact of loss of competitive advantages on Investment Opportunities.
5. Evaluate the possible impact of customer dissatisfaction on Investment Opportunities.
6. Evaluate the possible impact of rigidity on Investment Opportunities.
7. Evaluate the possible impact of red tape on Investment Opportunities.
8. Evaluate the possible impact of conflict on Investment Opportunities
9. Evaluate the possible impact of duplication on Investment Opportunities
10. Evaluate the possible impact of on bureaucratic corruption Investment Opportunities.
11. Evaluate the possible impact of reduced operational efficiency on Investment Opportunities.
12. Evaluate the possible impact of limitations in employee's potential and Capabilities on Investment Opportunities.

13. Practical recommendation and suggestions will be given.

5. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

In order to accomplish the objectives of this research paper, the following questions were set.

1. Is there a relationship between slower or delay in decision-making and Investment Opportunities?
2. Is there a relationship between centralized lengthy procedures and Investment Opportunities?
3. Is there a relationship between lack of transparency and Investment Opportunities?
4. Is there a relationship between loss of competitive advantages and Investment Opportunities?
5. Is there a relationship between customer dissatisfaction and Investment Opportunities?
6. Is there a relationship between rigidity and Investment Opportunities?
7. Is there a relationship between red tape and Investment Opportunities?
8. Is there a relationship between conflict and Investment Opportunities?
9. Is there a relationship between duplication and Investment Opportunities?
10. Is there a relationship between bureaucratic corruption and Investment Opportunities?
11. Is there a relationship between reduced operational efficiency and Investment Opportunities?
12. Is there a relationship between limitations in employees' potential and capabilities and Investment Opportunities?

5. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Foreign and local investment play important role in the development of the economy. Over the last decade or so the government of Jordan has adopted many strategies to encourage overseas investment in Jordan. Direct and indirect foreign investments is among the deep concerns of His Majesty King Abdullah. In his world tours, his majesty tries to market Jordan as a place that pays off any investment. According to (Senkuku1 & Gharleghi, 2015) a cross –border investment is important for economy development, hence countries should maintain good relationships with investors. Unfortunately, overall investment is negatively influenced by the type of systems and structures that prevail in the operations of local governments. Government attempts to attract and retain investors should go in parallel lines with new form of bureaucracy that replaces the old-fashioned bureaucracy. Rapid change, advancement of technology and the inevitable changing business environments form the ground floor for modern and flexible bureaucratic systems. Larbi (2003) stated that government should adopt more flexible, flatter and responsive structures and decentralize their management practices. The association between these bureaucratic problem and investment opportunities have been neglected in most research papers. This study is aimed to provide a conceptual practical framework to ease the effect of these problems on investments opportunities. Finally, it hoped that, this study might benefit researchers, investors, government authorities and anybody who would have benefit in this area of study.

7. SCOPE OF THE STUDY

Critical review of existing published materials on bureaucracy problems finalized that the adoption of extreme or excessive bureaucracy reduces investors desire to invest in a particular country. Governments need to generate effective policies and strategies to accommodate the acceleration of businesses, reduce the rising cost of bureaucracy and increase businesses ability to respond to market changes and fluctuations. Careful understanding of the nature of bureaucracy, the accurate diagnosis of bureaucracy problems and the analysis of their impact on investment potentials are crucial to diagnose the exact impact of bureaucratic problems and how they are related to investment decisions in Jordan and worldwide. The comprehensive evaluation of bureaucracy problems with deep concentration on the following twelve problems: slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive

advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employee's potential and capabilities are discussed as potential problems to investment in Jordan. Thereafter became the scope of this study.

Demographic factors are important categorical in this study. Jordan is located in the Middle East; and it has population of approximately 11 million. Jordan is ranked among countries that are safe and secure place for investments. Targeted population consisted of random 240 respondents. As with other research papers time constraints, logistical constraints and lack of financial resources are all pressing constrains that have considerable effect on the conduction of this research paper. Fortunately, and to the best of researcher's abilities, these constraints effects were eased so as not to affect the overall objectives of the study.

8. REVIEW OF LITERTURE

8.1. *Meaning of Bureaucracy*

Bureaucracy is an old organizational structure used in many countries all over the world Bureaucracy is defined as multiple separate government departments with independent decisions and authorities (Longley, 2019). Bureaucracy is present in all types of sectors. According to Woodrow (2010) bureaucracy as a system exists in all types of organizations being it public or private. It exists in banks, in insurance companies.in hospitals, in universities and so on. The pioneer contributor to bureaucracy is Max Weber. Weber stated that, bureaucracy is seen as the best organizational system to manage large organizations. This because elements of bureaucracy like order, discipline and division of work help organizations to work effectively. According to (Roth & Wittich, 2013) Weber's characteristics are applicable to all modern organizations. These characteristics include: hierarchical chain of command, strong division of work, clearly defined goals, clearly written rules and procedures and so on.

Despite what so called "Bureaucratic idealism" and its general application, many studies have emphasized the fact that the adoption of extreme bureaucracy have become problematic to a large number of organizations especially those who intend to use advanced technologies combined with scientific management development. Well as scientific and management development (Mohammed et al., 2013). The bureaucratic obstacle relates to many parties involved; the organization, the communities, the group and individual investors and the economy in general. Excessiveness of bureaucracy is said to kill innovation, reduces competitiveness, and restricts development, wastes the efforts to attract foreign investors and hence losing investment opportunities. This best illustrated by (Dobrescu and et al., 2012). According to them and till to day entrepreneurs still suffer from bureaucratic problems and find it difficult to interact with public institutions and their officials. Other researchers stated that, the application of excessive bureaucracy should be reduced in an attempt to eliminate its negative impacts. (Gabriel, 2014).

8.2. *Investment*

Investment means the employment of capital in profitable ventures. Capital owners seek to invest in secure projects that yield high returns with less risk. According to Mahiti (2012), developed countries highly appreciate the importance of foreign investment. Foreign investment in any country is important because such investment facilitates growth; provide capital and multiple skills and shares risks and technology transfer with national projects. To facilitate foreign investment governments should formulate modern policies and adopt more effective measures; at the same time improving the existing ones. According to Charles (2008), doing so will boost gross domestic products and increases export earnings. Domestic investment is the other face of the coin. The importance of domestic trade should never be neglected or undermined. According to (Bahrulmazi et al., 2014) there is a rising concern for governments to reconcile both foreign investment and domestic trade and hence make serious attempts to consciously "review investment policy that allows for free repatriation of profits and capital gains generated from domestic operations". Over the past decade, Jordan has introduced the following measures to become a country with an open and prosperous economy: reforming its investment and business policies, improving its reputation as an attractive destination for investment, diversifying its economy, and stimulating business and the

creation of new investment laws in 2014. All these measure aimed to improves Jordan's reputation as an attractive destination for investment. (Mikazda & Alhajahmad, 2018). Unfortunately, the adoption of bureaucratic system limits the above ambitions. The relationship between bureaucratic systems and investors desire to invest is no secret anymore. Bureaucratic obstacles have negative impact on investor's desire to invest. Landstrom (2005) commented that bureaucracy and its demerits affects negatively business environments. Therefore, to take advantage of both existing and potential investments governments must find clear-cut remedies for all Bureaucratic problems and their associated effects.

8.3. Operational Definitions of Bureaucracy problems

8.3.1. Slower or delay in decision making

In bureaucratic systems, the process of decisions making is made under strict and official codes of rules and regulations. According to Swanson (2017) bureaucratic have distinctive structures and official rigid procedures which tend to slow the decision making process. This of course makes organizations unable to compete in dynamic changing environments. Hence, meeting customers' demands tend to be slow too. The adherence to these rigid rules and regulations leads to unnecessary delays in the overall processes of the organization. Business environments requires decisive, fast-paced decisions and immediate reactions. All these are luxuries that bureaucratic systems cannot afford or comply with.

8.3.2. Centralized & Formalization

Centralization is common phenomena in most bureaucratic organizations. Delegation is at its minimum levels and power is highly centralized. Centralization is normally linked with formalization. Pandey (2011) concluded that most government organizations have considerable elements of bureaucratic control mechanisms and formalization. Centralization can be defined as the distribution of authority a cross the organizational structure. (Hsu et al., 1983) gave a specific definition of centralization as the formal distribution of authority within the organizational structure. On the other hand, Formalization is defined as the accomplishment of tasks under strict control of rules and procedures, as suggested by (Organ & Greene, 1981). Others like Armandi & Jr (1985) stressed that formalization leads to tasks standardization, at the same time negative sanctions can be imposed to deal with rules violations. In bureaucratic context, both centralization and formalization yield the following disadvantages: innovation among people is limited; inability to delegate the decision-making authority and the employees' autonomy is restricted by bureaucracy (Jaskyte, 2011).

8.3.3. Lack of Transparency

In general, public bodies and public institutions are assigned the task of providing information and make it available to the public. Relevant, essential data, feedback and timely information about economic activities is needed to facilitate investment decisions. According to Magnini et al., (2000) government's institutions and departments should provide thorough, timely. Complete, accessible and transparent information to all parties who need it

8.3.4. Loss of Competitive Advantages

Competitive advantage is an advantage gained over competitors. Competitive advantages include lower prices, better quality, and greater benefits given to customers and enhanced after sales services. According to UK Essays November 2018) competitive advantage is an advantage over competitors gained by offering consumers greater value, either by means of lower prices or by providing greater benefits and service that justifies higher prices. Unfortunately, Competitive advantages can be lost because of excessive internal bureaucratic procedures that are adopted by the public sector organizations. These bureaucratic procedures create ambiguity and uncertainty, which in return affects the effectiveness and workings of this essential sector.

8.3.5. Customer Dissatisfaction

Many argue that bureaucracy have effective framework to organize things. Unfortunately, the way these things are managed tend to be slower and less effective. Because of this, many customers feel dissatisfied. Swanson (2017) stated that, bureaucratic organizations involve huge elements of files, heavy paperwork and rigid registration processes and procedures.

8.3.6. Rigidity

In general, the term rigidity means stiffness and lack of flexibility. Great deal of research emphasized that bureaucratic systems tend to have rules and regulations that are rigid and inflexible. According to internet source date: (na) "rigid compliance with rules and regulations discourages initiative and creativity. It may also provide the cover to avoid responsibility for failures"

8.3.7. Red Tape

In general, the term red tape means the existence of official processes or routines, procedures, regulations, forms and excessive amount of paper work required to gain bureaucratic approval for accomplishing something. According to Woodrow (2010). These routine processes waste time, hinder production and slow down the bureaucracy's ability to provide a service to the public.

8.3.8. Conflict

Conflict means the goals of various bureaucratic bodies or authorities do not conform or simply do not match with each other. Hence, they end up working at cross-purposes. Adamolekun (1999) argued that conflict in interest between equal, unequal parties exist in all types organizations, and bureaucracy is no exception. Furthermore, Ibeto CJ (2020) confirmed that conflict is a universal phenomenon and is found in all types of social gatherings. Conflict could arise either deliberately or deliberately through the implementation of government policies and procedures.

8.3.9. Duplication

Duplication is the act of doing the same thing. One noticeable feature of bureaucratic doings is doing the very same thing repeatedly. Repetition waste time and money. "Duplication refers to situations where there are multiple copies or instances of something in an organization. It is where more than one individual or entity may be involved in doing the same work or making decisions about something without any clear coordination between them"(internet source, date: na).

8.3.10. Bureaucratic Corruption

Corruption is the act of dishonesty. Officials practice this dishonest behavior across all levels of the organization. Corruption occurs in all types of sectors being it private or public. Corruption can take many forms and practices. Chen (2021) stated that, "corruption can include giving or accepting bribes or inappropriate gifts, double-dealing, under-the-table transactions, manipulating elections, diverting funds, laundering money, and defrauding investors". If corruption practices go undermined, users of public services will make investors and customers lose trust in practices and products.

8.3.11. Reduced Operational Efficiency

Modern organizations operate in a very competitive global business environment. In order to survive and achieve objectives, modern organizations must work on their operational efficiency by adopting modern and flexible organizational structures that adopts easily to globalization, modernization and innovation. Strong presence of rigidity, lengthy rules and procedures hinders overall operational efficiency, hence makes bureaucratic systems unsuitable for modern organizations. In line with this, Hamel (2012)) stressed that organization exist and operate in competitive environments, hence management must reinvent their systems, practices in order to survive the ever changing environments.

8.3.12. Limitations in Employee's Potential and Capabilities.

Unfortunately, among the biggest demerits of bureaucracy is the limitation of employee's potential and capabilities. In bureaucratic systems employee's potential and capabilities are undermined, because their

working environment and their overall organizational structure lack the ability to adopt modernization. According to internet source (date: na) many researchers believe that departmentation and strong division of work may bring some benefits to organizations. On the other hand, these characteristics limit employee's potentials and capabilities.

In general, the disputes regarding the bureaucracy dimensions and their associated problems still in progress. According to (Montrio & Adler, 2022) organizational bureaucratic forms are still present and dominant in many organizations. They also stated that, bureaucracy as a principle and as a paradigmatic form of an organization should be studied together in an attempt to overcome the decentralized, reified and atomized ways in which bureaucracy is viewed. Other researchers like (Besely et al., 2022) argued that there is still misunderstanding regarding the role of bureaucracy in the development of economies. They also stated that large bureaucratic reforms that involve multiple interdependent dimensions could encourage economic development. The work of Lea (2021) came to support the findings of other researchers in that despite bureaucracy fails in some places, betrayals and explicit critiques; there is still a desire for bureaucratic systems and practices. Accordingly, bureaucracy continues to produce public benefits and aspirations.

Lopes & Vieira (2023) found that in Latin America for example, many government practices and most public appointments are influenced by the contextual factors of bureaucracy such as loyalty and rigidity; while in Europe nominations are based on strict rules and well-defined management structures as the case of United Kingdom and France. According to them, rigidity and strict rules and well-defined management structures are all important dimensions of bureaucracy. Furthermore, Jordan, (2019) concluded that bureaucratic systems cannot be dismantled at all. However, the useful aspects of bureaucracy can be of an advantage to the organization. While the un-useful aspects can be eliminated using modern non-human technologies.

9. RESEARCH THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Bureaucratic systems have been practiced for a long time. Many organizations such as government departments, army authorities, both public and private companies, hospitals, courts, universities and schools have widely adopted bureaucratic systems to fulfill tasks. However, the shift towards modernization and globalization have forced many organizations to depart from using bureaucratic systems because such systems can stand against modernization, which is an important factor to enhance investment opportunities.

The framework of this research is illustrated diagrammatically based on a thorough revision of published literature on the topic of bureaucracy and its relationship with investment. The current research is based on the assumptions that the independent variables such as slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employees' potential and capabilities had a negative impact on the dependent variables (investment opportunities). Figure (1) is the illustration of the theoretical framework, which takes into account all listed constructs that may affect investment opportunities in Jordan.

Figure (1): Theoretical Framework Of The study.

Prepared by: Authors (2023)

10. HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

The main hypothesis of this study are as follows:

- Ho: Slower or delay in decision making has no impact on investment opportunities in Jordan
- H1: Slower or delay in decision making has impact on investment opportunities in Jordan
- Ho: Centralized & Formalization has no impact on investment opportunities in Jordan
- H2: Centralized & Formalization has impact on investment opportunities in Jordan
- Ho: Lack of transparency has no impact on investment opportunities in Jordan
- H3: Lack of transparency has impact on investment opportunities in Jordan
- Ho: Loss of competitive advantages has no impact on investment opportunities in Jordan
- H4: Loss of competitive advantages has impact on investment opportunities in Jordan

- Ho: Customer dissatisfaction has no impact on investment opportunities in Jordan
H5: Customer dissatisfaction has impact on investment opportunities in Jordan.
Ho: Rigidity has no impact on investment opportunities in Jordan.
H6: Rigidity has impact on investment opportunities in Jordan.
Ho: Red Tape has no impact on investment opportunities in Jordan.
H7: Red Tape has impact on investment opportunities in Jordan.
Ho: Conflict has no impact on investment opportunities in Jordan.
H8: Conflict has impact on investment opportunities in Jordan.
Ho: Duplication has no impact on investment opportunities in Jordan.
H9: Duplication has impact on investment opportunities in Jordan.
Ho: Bureaucratic Corruption has no impact on investment opportunities in Jordan.
H10: Bureaucratic Corruptions has impact on investment opportunities in Jordan.
Ho: Reduced Operational Efficiency has no impact on investment opportunities in Jordan.
H11: Reduced Operational Efficiency has impact on investment opportunities in Jordan
Ho: Limitations in employee's potential and capabilities has no impact on investmen opportunities in Jordan.
H12: Limitations in employee's potential and capabilities has impact on investment opportunities in Jordan.

11. METHODOLOGY OF RESEARCH

11.1. Research Design

A well-structured questionnaire is used to collect primary information from 280-targeted respondents. Quantitative approach is adopted and SPSS version 16 is used to analyze the data collected through the questionnaires. Figures and tables are shown to make readings and interpretations easier regarding the effect of slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employees' potential and capabilities on investment opportunities in Jordan. The chosen method is known for its convenience and compatibility in this kind of research. Furthermore, the chosen method allows gathering information from wider audience. Finally, this method of collecting information is known for its economies in terms of time and resources.

11.2. Target Population

(Saunders et al., 2003) defined the term population as the entire set of data in which the researcher has interest. On the other hand, the targeted population is the set of data from which the proposed sample is taken; in this case the actual investors who have actually invested in Jordan. The targeted population is approximately 280 investors. This number includes local investors and expatriate investors. The characteristics of the targeted population are listed in table (1)

Table (1): The distribution of Target population

Composition of Population	Numbers	Percentages
1. Approximate numbers for Local investors (in all sectors)	2900	0.640
1. Approximate numbers for Foreign investors (in all sectors)	1600	0.360
Total Target Population	4500	100

Table sources: Researchers 2023

11.3. Sample Size of the Study

The sample size is normally selected from the targeted population. The sample size selected should be convenient, sufficient and representative of the entire population.

Raosoft (2004) suggested that 200 respondents should be convenient and representative of the entire population at confidence level of 95% with marginal error of 5%. This of course meets the criteria of analyses.

11.4. Instrument of the Research

To collect all needed information two instruments were used:

11.4(a). Primary Data

A structured questionnaire is used to enable respondents to give direct, standard, unbiased and objective answers. This mechanism allows results to be numerically. Still as with other types of collecting information attitudes of respondents towards filling the questionnaires could present serious limitations to the study and its findings.

Section.1: Five items are addressed to collect demographic data such as nationality of investors, size of investment, value of investment, location of investment and investment sectors.

Section.2: Contains twelve items (as listed in Research Theoretical Framework). The purpose of that list is to seek data about the possible impact of bureaucracy problems on investment opportunities "the case of investment potentials in Jordan".

11.4(b). Source of Secondary Data: these sources include recent publications, assays, reviews, reports and so on.

11.5. Validity and Reliability of Used Instruments

For the sake of maintaining validity and ensuring reliability of the questionnaire is referred to professional, experts, scholars and investors to check on appropriateness and consistency. The instrument used is found to be sound, consistent and reliable with reliability test of 0.766%.

11.6. Data Collection

280 questionnaires were randomly distributed among investors. This accounts up to 7% of the total targeted population, which approximates 4500 according to government statistics. Table.2 shows summery of all statistics regarding the distribution, returns, useable, non-useable and non-responses to questionnaires. Non-response may be due to unwillingness to fill them or that respondents are not interested in the study.

Table (2): Summary of Distributed, Returned, Useable, on-response Questionnaires

Condition	Distribution of Questionnaires		Returned Questionnaires		Usable Questionnaires		Un- useable Questionnaires		Non- Response	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
Number of Investors	280	100	230	82	200	72	30	11	50	18

Source of the table: Researchers 2023.

11.7. Procedures

Required data were collected through the distribution of 17 items well- structured random among foreign and local investors. Practical instructions, guidance and assistance were given to Instructions, guidance and assistance were given to ensure the correct filling of the questionnaire. Researchers confirmed that confidentiality of responses. The scoring of responses is carried out as followed:

Section.1: Scores are not attached for (Bio-Data).

Section. 2: Contains all variables. Five point Likert's scale is used to rate responses and to see the extent to respondents react to items mentioned in the questionnaire. Rating of responses is shown in table (3):

Table (3): Mean Rating of responses to questionnaire items

Category of response	Abbreviations	Points	Bounding- unit
Strongly Agree	SA	5	4.60 -5.00
Agree	AG	4	3.60 -4.59
Un-Decided	UN	3	2.60 -3.59
Disagree	DA	2	1.60 -2.59
Strongly Disagree	SD	1	1.00 – 1.59

Source: Prepared by Researchers 2022

12. DATA ANALYSSIS & MAIN FINDINGS

For maintaining consistency and completeness of responses, careful over all editing is carried out to reduce gaps and mistakes. Once done that SPSS version 16 is used for analytical analyses. The use of this statistical package is beneficial for the production of descriptive and inferential statistics. Analyses outputs include percentages, graphs, and tables and so on. On the other hand, inferential statistics like Pearson Correlations and linear regressions are used to determine the strength of relationships between variables and hence test the listed hypotheses.

12. 1 Respondents Demographic Factors Profile.

Table (4): Frequency Distribution of Respondents Demographics

Sequence	Demographic- Items	Frequency	Percent	Valid- %	Cumulative %
1	Nationality of investors				
	Jordanians Investors	110	55.00	55.00	55.00
	Foreign Investors	90	45.00	45.00	100
2	Size of Investment				
	Large projects investments	90	45.00	45.00	45.00
	Medium projects investments	50	25.00	25.00	70.00
	Small projects investments	60	30.00	30.00	100
3	Value of Investment				
	Big Value investments	90	45.00	45.00	45.00
	Medium Value investments	50	25.00	25.00	70.00
	Small Value investments	60	30.00	30.00	100
4	Location of Investment				
	Investments in the North	80	40.00	40.00	40.00
	Investments in the South	60	30.00	30.00	70.00
	Investments in the East	20	10.00	10.00	90.00
	Investments in the West	40	20.00	20.00	100
5	Investment Sectors				
	Manufacturing Sector	50	25.00	25.00	25.00
	Service Sector	30	15.00	15.00	40.00
	Agriculture Sector	25	12.50	12.50	52.50
	Health Sector	30	15.00	15.00	67.50
	Tourism Sector	35	17.50	17.50	85
	IT Sector	20	10.00	10.00	95
	Others	10	0.05	5.00	100
Total		200	100	100	100

Table (4): Provide the following indications

1) Nationality of Investors Indicators:

Table. 4 indicates that Jordanian investors have a percentage of 110(55%) of the total numbers of investments while the proportion of foreign investment is 90 (45) of overall total investments. This tendency indicate that Jordanian Economy is locally built. Most capital comes from Jordanian who work in gulf countries and they tend to invest in their homeland. Foreign investment still moderate in numbers due to many obstacles. It is important to mention that, if foreign investment is to increase governments should use all measures and show more capabilities to facilitate potential investments.

2) Size of Investment:

Table 4 indicates that large projects investments with a total of 90 (45%) are dominant among other sizes of investment. The practical explanation for that, the government of Jordan try to attract and encourage big overseas investments to attain required economic growth and at the same time increase employment opportunities for the citizens of Jordan.

3) Value of Investment:

Table 4 indicates that big value projects investments with a total of 90 (45%) are dominant among other values of investment. The explanation for that is the attempts of governments to attract and encourage big value investments to encourage the inflow and circulation of capital. It should be noted that size of investment and value of investment are interrelated.

4) *Location Of Investment:*

Table 4 show that 80 (45%) investments are located in the north of Jordan because most capitals are geared towards the north of Jordan. Investors prefer locations that are near Amman because of availability of human resources, availability of materials, the presence of infrastructure, facilities and so on.

5) *With Respect To Investment Sectors:*

Table 4 shows that the highest investment portions with percentage of 50(25%) found in the manufacturing sector followed by 35 (17.50 %) investments in the tourism sector. In Jordan, the manufacturing sector and the tourism sector are the most crucial pillars of the Jordanian economy. Because of Jordan's location, many investors perceive Jordan as a promising and safe land for prosperous investments.

12.2. *Reliability Analyses*

Full account of information along with objectives of the study are used to determine the independent variables such as: the impact of slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employees' potential and capabilities on the dependent variable investment opportunities in Jordan. The target population is amounted to 280 respondents. The response rate is 72% which is approximately 200 respondents is said to be satisfactory to make logical conclusions the expected effect of slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employees' potential and capabilities on investment opportunities in Jordan. Once the responses were scored, Cronbach's Alpha is used to determine the reliability of the tool. It is generally accepted that if values of questionnaires items are more than Alpha values, then that indicates the consistency, soundness, and reliability of the scale. Cronbach's Alpha values are shown in table (5).

Table (5): Reliability Table

SN	Constructs	Number of items	Cronbach's values
1	Slower or Delay in Decision Making	01	0.833
2	Centralized Lengthy Procedures	01	0.824
3	Lack of Transparency	01	0.892
4	Loss of Competitive Advantages	01	0.822
5	Customer Dissatisfaction	01	0.849
6	Rigidity	01	0.866
7	Red Tape	01	0.862
8	Conflict	01	0.822
9	Duplication	01	0.880
10	Bureaucratic Corruption	01	0.866
11	Reduced Operational Efficiency	01	0.876
12	limitation in employees' potential and capabilities	01	0.856
11	The Entire Questionnaire	17	0.844

High Alpha values give more reliable generated scale. Cooper & Shindler (2007) stated that 0.70 is statistically acceptable reliability coefficient. Table. 5 shows the reliability values of the stated variable which ranges from 0.822 to 0.89. These values are higher than the prescribed threshold value of ($\alpha = 0.70$). In comparison the Cronbach's Alpha value are compatible with the reliability test of the conducted present study. Hence the scale is said to be sound and reliable.

12.3. *Validity Analyses*

Based on statistical analyses, validity analyses were carried out to determine the impact of slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employees' potential and capabilities as the independent variables and investment opportunities in Jordan as the dependent variable. The intention of these analyses is to eliminate the volume of redundant information. Table .6 shows that items covered in the study has scored more than 0.30 which is the minimum requirement for inclusion in the study as suggested by (Hair et al., 2020). Applying this rule, no items were found redundant. Table 6. Shows factor analyses for all items mentioned in the questionnaire.

Table (6): Factor Analysis on of slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employees' potential and capabilities on investment opportunities

SN	Variables	Variables' Measures
1	Slower or Delay in Decision Making Measure	0.850
2	Centralized Lengthy Procedures Measure	0.835
3	Lack of Transparency Measure	0.822
4	Loss of Competitive Advantages Measure	0.830
5	Customer Dissatisfaction Measure	0. 819
6	Rigidity Measure	0.860
7	Red Tape Measure	0.825
8	Conflict Measure	0.862
9	Duplication Measure	0.837
10	Bureaucratic Corruption Measure	0. 849
11	Reduced Operational Efficiency Measure	0.820
12	limitation in employees' potential and capabilities	0.834
11	The Entire Questionnaire	0.832

12.4. Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics such as means and standard deviations were tabulated. Means values signifies the level of agreeableness and disagreeableness of respondents to items mentioned in the questionnaire. On the other hand, values of the standard deviations confirm the issue of variability. Computation of means and standard deviations are shown in table. 7

Table (7): Rates of slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employees' potential and capabilities on investment opportunities

Section	Description of Items	Descriptive Statistics	
		Mean	SD
1	Slower or Delay in Decision Making Measure	4.42	0.74
2	Centralized Lengthy Procedures Measure	4.53	0.78
3	Lack of Transparency Measure	4.52	0.81
4	Loss of Competitive Advantages Measure	4.69	0.83
5	Customer Dissatisfaction Measure	4.32	0.76
6	Rigidity Measure	4.54	0.73
7	Red Tape Measure	4.63	0.82
8	Conflict Measure	4.48	0.77
9	Duplication Measure	4.29	0.72
10	Bureaucratic Corruption Measure	4.39	0.71
11	Reduced Operational Efficiency Measure	4.28	0.73
12	limitation in employees' potential and capabilities	4.27	0.76
11	Investment opportunities	4.18	0.77

Table (7) shows the ranking of respondents concerning the impact of slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employees' potential and capabilities as the independent variables and investment opportunities as the dependent variables.

The" independent variables (1-12) have means range from (4.18-4.68) and the range for standard deviations range is (0.71-0.82). These ranges for the means and the standard deviations confirms that, most respondents agree on the statement that all set of the independent variables have impact on investment opportunities.

Table (7) reveals that the mean ranges from low value of 4, 18 to a high value of 4, 69. This indicates that the impact of slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employees' potential and capabilities on investment opportunities is considerable. On investment opportunities. Expressed in figures, the range of means for independent variables (4.27- 4.69) >4.120, this indicates that investment opportunities are influenced by slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employees' potential and capabilities.

12.5. Inferential Statistics

12.5(a). Pearson Correlation Coefficients

Pearson's correlation coefficients measure the strength of association between variable embodied in the study. Normally the association ranges from -1to 1+Furthermore, the significance of relationships is social science is normally determined at conventional significance level between p=0.01 and p= 0.05. The correlation matrix for independent and dependent variables are exhibited in table (8).

Table (8): Correlation Matrix for all variables of the study*

Study Variables	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
1	1.00											
2	0.74	1.00										
3	0.79	0.73	1.00									
4	0.78	0.70	0.72	1.00								
5	0.70	0.79	0.59	0.73	1.00							
6	0.78	0.70	0.71	0.70	0.71	1.00						
7	0.71	0.73	0.72	0.73	0.72	0.79	1.00					
8	0.75	0.73	0.71	0.72	0.74	0.71	0.74	1.00				
9	0.70	0.71	0.72	0.73	0.73	0.78	0.79	0.72	1.00			
10	0.79	0.70	0.71	0.72	0.72	0.77	0.76	0.77	0.78	1.00		
11	0.78	0.70	0.71	0.70	0.71	0.79	0.72	0.73	0.72	0.71	1.00	
12	0.71	0.73	0.72	0.73	0.72	0.71	07	0.72	0.73	0.72	0.72	1.00

***Note: Coding of Variables include:**

(1= Slower or Delay in Decision Making, 2= Centralized Lengthy Procedures 3= Lack of Transparency, 4= Loss of Competitive Advantages, 5= Customer Dissatisfaction, 6= Rigidity, 7= Red Tape, 8= Conflict, 9= Duplication, 10= Bureaucratic Corruption, 11= Reduced Operational Efficiency, 12= Limitation in Employees' Potential and Capabilities)

Table (8) table 8 shows positive correlations between the stated independent and dependent variables. Here, it can be confirmed that slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of

transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employees' potential and capabilities and investment opportunities. The correlation is within the range of 0.70 to 0.79. The highest to lowest correlation is depicted between slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employees' potential and capabilities and investment opportunities. (In numbers $r = 0.79, 0.79, 0.78, 0.78, 0.78, 0.75, 0.74, 0.71, 0.71, 0.70, 0.70, P < 0.01$). This clearly indicates strong impact of bureaucracy problems on investment opportunities

Table (9): The coefficient values for of slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employees' potential and capabilities on investment opportunities

Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	Beta	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	0.422	0.043	0.418	3.166	0.006
Slower or Delay in Decision Making	0.561	0.041	0.504	4.122	0.041
Centralized Lengthy Procedures	0.593	0.040	0.509	4.144	0.049
Lack of Transparency	0.558	0.042	0.463	3.821	0.047
Loss of Competitive Advantages	0.531	0.039	0.521	4.208	0.044
Customer Dissatisfaction	0.545	0.041	0.509	4.187	0.041
Rigidity	0.569	0.041	0.503	4.110	0.042
Red Tape	0.548	0.042	0.493	3.917	0.049
Conflict	0.533	0.042	0.507	4.144	0.044
Duplication	0.588	0.039	0.516	3.821	0.042
Bureaucratic Corruption	0.561	0.041	0.511	4.208	0.047
Reduced Operational Efficiency	0.548	0.041	0.487	4.187	0.048
Limitation in Employees' Potential and Capabilities	0.529	0.042	0.463	4.110	0.042

Table (9) above shows the exact relationship between slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employees' potential and capabilities and investment opportunities. Results show that investment opportunities value is 0.422. Here, one unit in slower or delay in decision making would affect investment opportunities by 0.561. A unit enhancement in the centralized lengthy procedures would affect investment opportunities by 0.593. A unit modification in lack of transparency would yield investment opportunities by 0.558. One-unit increase in the loss of competitive advantages would affect investment opportunities by 0.531. One unit change in customer dissatisfaction affects investment opportunities by 0.545. One unit shift in rigidity impacts investment opportunities by 0.569. One-unit alteration of red tape affects investment opportunities by 0.548. One-unit compromise of conflict affects investment opportunities by 0.533. One-unit modification in duplication affects investment opportunities by 0.588. One unit move from corruption impacts investment opportunities by 0.561. One-unit improvement in reduced operational efficiency affects investment opportunities by 0.548. One-unit decrease in limitation of employees' potential and capabilities generate benefits in investment opportunities by 0.529. Centralized lengthy procedures has the greatest impact on investment opportunities. While the limitation in employees' potential and capabilities has the lowest effect on investment opportunities. For significance level of 5% and level of confidence at 95%, slower or delay in decision-making had 0.041 level of significance. Centralized lengthy procedures had 0.049 significance level. lack of transparency had 0.047 significance level. Loss of competitive advantages had 0.044 significance level. Customer dissatisfaction had 0.041 significance level. Red tape had 0.049 significance level. Conflict had 0.044 significance level. Duplication had 0.042 significance level. Bureaucratic Corruption had 0.047 significance level. Reduced operational efficiency had 0.048 significance level. Finally, Limitation in Employees' Potential and Capabilities had 0.042 significance level. The stated

sequence of variables is the most pressing bureaucratic problems, which in reality found to have strong impact on investment opportunities.

12.5(a) Regression Analysis (Hypothesis Testing)

In social sciences regression analysis is a normal procedure used to estimate the strength of relationships between independent and dependent variables. Consequently, linear regression model is used to test the logicality of hypothesis.

12.5 Slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employees' potential and capabilities on investment opportunities.

Table (10): Model Summary for slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employees' potential and capabilities on investment opportunities

Model No	R	R Square	Adjusted R-Square	Std Error	β Beta	F Value	T Value	Sig Level
(1) Slower or Delay in Decision Making & Investment Opportunities	.661	.422	.386	.951	.544	19.332	7.423	.000
(2) Centralized Lengthy Procedures & Investment Opportunities	.652	.421	.372	.946	.550	19.808	7.129	.000
(3) Lack of Transparency & Investment Opportunities	.621	.376	.363	.937	.508	19.108	7.182	.000
(4) Loss of Competitive Advantages & Investment Opportunities	.608	.362	.359	.931	.448	18.667	6.867	.000
(5) Customer Dissatisfaction & Investment Opportunities	.609	.377	.367	.942	.473	18.728	6.933	.000
(6) Rigidity & Investment Opportunities	.658	.423	.379	.948	.552	19.283	5.137	.000
(7) Red Tape & Investment Opportunities	.631	.396	.357	.937	.541	19.116	7.113	.000
(8) Conflict & Investment Opportunities	.592	.372	.349	.912	.422	17.492	6.752	.000
(9) Duplication & Investment Opportunities	.608	.362	.359	.921	.448	18.667	6.867	.000
(10) Bureaucratic Corruption & Investment Opportunities	.609	.377	.367	.932	.473	18.728	6.933	.000

(11) Reduced Operational Efficiency & Investment Opportunities	.658	.423	.379	.948	.552	19.283	5.137	.000
(12) Limitation in Employees' Potential and Capabilities& Investment Opportunities	.631	.396	.357	.927	.541	19.116	7.113	.000

Note: Beta Columns= Values for Standard Regression Coefficients

Beta= Shows the impact of standard deviation differences for independent variables on the dependent variables standard deviations.

Table. (10): shows the regression analysis for 12 models

Models (1-12): R square values implies that (42%,42% ,37%,36%,37% 42%,39%,37%,36%,37%, 42%,39%) variations exist in the dependent variable in this case investment opportunities this is due to the influence of the independent variables (slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employees' potential and capabilities). F values (19.332, 19. 808, 19.108, 18.667, 18.728, 19.283, 19.116, 17.492, 18.667, 18.728, 19.283, 19.116) shows that the model possess overall significance strength. Hence the models from 1-12 are correct. Using Beta coefficients the 12 models (slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employees' potential and capabilities) cause (54%, 55%, 50%, 44%, 47%, 55%,54% and 42%, 44%47%,55%,54%) positive variations in investment opportunities and t values (7.423, 7. 129 , 7.182 , 6.867, 6.933,6.137, 7.113, 6.752, 6.867, 6.933, 5.137 and 7.113 with p with P < 0.001. < 0.001. Therefore, HOS (1-12) declares that, there is: no impact of slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employees' potential and capabilities " are all rejected and H1 for all 12 models which implies that "there is an impact of slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employees' potential and capabilities " are all accepted.

13. RESEARCH FINDINGS

13. (1). Findings Discussion

The study intended to determine the impact of slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employees' potential and capabilities on investment opportunities. Majority of respondents confirmed that slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employees' potential and capabilities have impact on investment opportunities. Current research on the topic confirms that demographic factors are of considerable importance. In addition to that, field research showed tendency not to invest in Jordan due to bureaucratic problems. Weight of demographic factors are not the same for listed factors. For example, the factor concerning nationality of investors are parallel to recent research, which confirms the unequal

presentation of this factor. Findings of Ishak & Ramah (2002) confirmed that FDI has played an important role in the economic development of many developing countries. Therefore, equal presentation of foreign investors may open more research opportunities. The same argument is valid for the rest of demographic factors, which include size of investment, value of investment, location of investment and investment's sector. According to (Dobrescu et al., 2012) dominant bureaucratic problems hinder economic progress. Descriptive statistics provide strong evidence that respondents' profile and slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employees' potential and capabilities have impact on investment opportunities. Inferential statistics shown in tabulated forms like correlations, coefficients and regression analysis are generated from the 200 responses to questionnaires. Linear regressions were adopted to determine the possible relationships between the independent and dependent variables. F – Statistic values shows the significance level of this research. The current study demonstrate that p value is 0.000 which is < 0.05 hence the model of this research is statistically significant. This confirms that the independent variables have significant relationships with the dependent variables. Finally, the standardized values illustrate that listed bureaucratic problems have enormous negative impact on investment opportunities.

Supportive findings come from published research papers on bureaucratic problems and the impact of such problems on investment opportunities. One Supportive research is the work of Cruz & Keefer (2015) they demonstrated that "good bureaucratic performance emerges not from accountability to voters or citizens, but rather from programmatic parties that allow politicians to resist the client's practices that undermine bureaucratic effectiveness". Current research findings are highly consistent to some published research findings, which the authors have read during their literature review. Further support comes from the work of Larbi, (2003) in which it is argued that separation of functions, the adoption of flexible, flatter and more responsive structures and the decentralization of management authorities within the public agencies give freedom manage with clear responsibility.

13. (2). Practical Implications of the Study

Excessive bureaucracy systems still prevail in many countries despite the tendency for modernization and liberalization. The way of conducting businesses in today's sittings is no longer similar to old days. Globalization forced many countries to introduce and use tactical reforms to reduce the evils of bureaucracy. The adoption of e-government has made the world to use simplified, transparent and accountable administrative regulations in order to make businesses establishment and dealings simpler in terms of time and money. Comprehensive approach is used to study the constructs that have impact on investment opportunities. Current findings show variations in the impacts of constructs on investment opportunities. Consequently, the following managerial implication are given as followed: to improve the chances for more investment, all bureaucratic and non-bureaucratic obstacles should be removed. Harmony should exist between bureaucratic systems and investors' perceptions. This leads to correct balancing of the constructs and shift away from the criteria of under estimation. Here it is suggested that accurate and well defines information is to be given to investors to help them make correct investment decisions. Secondly, government authorities and officials need to alter all stiff bureaucratic regimes that cut down numbers of investments. Furthermore, bureaucracy principles should be applied effectively and not subjectively to maintain ultimate performance across all government departments Thirdly, public servants must allow investors to have access for necessary information in order to facilitate their investment. Transparent transmission of complete required information would generate positive effects on investment opportunities. Fourthly, the combined 12-model approach could help both government officials and investors to better understanding of the complex nature of investment and the urgencies for well-modified procedures. Number five, government bodies and government decision makers should concentrate on all means that encourage and facilitate both domestic and foreign investments starting from giving positive impressions to the stage where actual investments are finally made. To facilitate these government bodies and authorities need to decentralize their authorities, cut down their lengthy procedures and make investment environment and procedures more user friendly. Finally, the 12-model approach can help government bodies to make decisive decisions to allure the negative impacts and generate more attractive investment environment.

13. 3. Conclusions

This research finding along with empirical research findings reveal that bureaucratic problems can negatively affect investment opportunities. The researchers have emphasized that demographic characteristics are of considerable importance towards investment opportunities. Furthermore, findings of this research confirmed that the slower or delay in decision making, centralized lengthy procedures, lack of transparency, loss of competitive advantages, customer dissatisfaction, rigidity, red tape, conflict, duplication, bureaucratic corruption, reduced operational efficiency and limitation in employees' potential and capabilities have impact on investment opportunities. The researcher, concluded that public service providers need to adopt more effective bureaucratic systems, introduce modern and attractive investment packages, cut short on their rules and regulations, set more space for innovation. Innovation within bureaucratic structures allow for the introduction of smart technologies with new techniques and practices, which helps government departments to operate more effectively. Not only that but also offer more e-services to meet e-market needs and satisfy customer needs and wants. Finally, the improvement of investment e- services would of course yield higher rate of investment. Alignment and continuous careful solutions to bureaucratic problems will surely increase investment potentials and hence get more sustainable economic growth.

13. 4. Recommendations

The following practical recommendations are given:

- Governments must highly stress the importance of procedural transparency and accountability, as well as strengthen its enforcement mechanisms.
- Governments should adopt bureaucracy that is more professional and employ civil servants who have noticeable competencies and long experience in the field of foreign investments.
- Governments should establish "unique offices" across regions to help investors to overcome difficulties that face them in starting up their investments.
- Governments should draw clear dividing lines between the issues of bureaucracy and professionalism existing in all public departments that deal with investors and investments. The interaction of these issue is vital for planning, programming and implementation of investments tasks and procedures.
- Governments should spend a great deal of efforts to improve the procedures for customs declarations, the procedures for visa grant, the procedures for residence permits at the same time they have to work hardly to prosper the efficiency of operating system air ports, sea ports and road exits.
- Governments must carry out regular evaluations and provide conscious feedback to keep current investors and attract new ones.
- Governments should give clear and accurate information on all matters that relate to investment in Jordan. In this instance all types of social media should be used to communicate with investors in order to speed up investment decision and finish up business
- Governments should practice more innovative supervisions on the civil service sector to eliminate or at least reduce corruption.

14. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Like most research, current paper has many limitations: First, variable measurements are based on the attitudes and perceptions of the respondents while filling the questionnaire. Second, the study was conducted in Jordan with concentration on investors already invested in Jordan. Should the study conducted in countries other than Jordan, surely the findings would vary a lot; consequently, the present findings cannot be generalized. Furthermore, illiteracy as a demographic factor was ignored. Third, valuable research papers, publications, books, articles and statistics were not looked at; making the selection suffers the element of bias and subjectivity. Four, the selected sample size is relatively small for the generalization of findings, hence. This relatively small sample size made it difficult to find more significant relationship from the data collected. Five, time constraints: the available time for this research was problematic in that the research was conducted in a period of nearly 4 months. This time length made difficult for authors to take their time regarding all over the completely practical steps of preparing this paper. Six, financial constraints have tied

up the hands of the researchers. No financial support is given for the authors; hence, the authors who have limited budgets and incomes pay all expenses incurred. Seven, the study used quantitative approach only. The qualitative approach on the other hand, can generate more analysis more without being constrained with predetermined techniques and procedures. Eight, it should be noted that the current research investigated bureaucratic problems in general terms rather than full appreciation of these problems. Nine, Access to some important data is limited specially information from governments departments. In addition, respondents denied access to their information because such information is regarded as confidential. Ten, some people who may be affected in the subject of this study had weak interest in the area of this research, therefore were not co-operative. Finally, lack of prior research studies on this topic was a troublesome and not available especially in Jordan.

15. FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

This study confirmed the strong impact of the twelve listed independent variables on investment opportunities. In this aspect, the following research directions are suggested:

1. Researchers who are interested in this topic are highly encouraged to carry out research on each and every independent variable in order to produce more significant and valid relationships between every single bureaucratic problem and investment opportunities.
2. It is recommended that larger sample size is to be taken. Surely, larger random samples give more representative distribution of the population and hence give relationships that are more significant.
3. It is proposed that future research can solely address the same research problem for service sector investors. Once done that, the results can be compared to produce more significant practical relationships. Such relationships can be used to improve the working of the public sector departments and then consolidate it to potential investors.
4. It is also suggested that future research addressing the same research problem is to be carried out in other parts of the world and in different cultures. Once again the results and can be later compared to produce more precise solutions to bureaucracy problems.
5. Future research on this topic should be given more time space and hence raise the time pressure which burdens the research methodology and outcomes.
6. Industrial financial support from both manufacturing and service sectors can improve the conditions under which future research is carried out. For example, the distribution and collection of questionnaires, typing and so on.
7. Improve lines of communication and understanding between government public officials and present or potential investors. Effective communication and better understanding can prevent infractions and maintain easement integrity.
8. More methodological work is needed on how to significantly capture the impact and outcomes of public policies towards the adoption of bureaucratic systems and their expected problems.
9. Finally, it is suggested that future research should focus on producing unified policies and coherent strategies to eliminate or at least minimize the cost of bureaucratic problems for all involved parties.

Acknowledgment

Many thanks to all respondents for their time and patience when filling the questionnaires. Sincere and deep thanks also extended to those who helped us in the distribution and collection of the returned questionnaires. Finally, many thanks to all for their valuable comments and suggestions while preparing this research paper. May God al mighty bless us all

Disclosure Statement

The authors are not aware of any affiliations, memberships, funding, or financial holdings that might be perceived as affecting the objectivity of this paper

Conflict of interests

Authors declare that no competing interests exist.

Data Availability Statement: Data that supports the findings of this study are available any time from corresponding author (M.R. Salah) upon reasonable request.

Authors Contribution's Statement: Corresponding author (M.R.S) and Co-author (E.A.R) confirm that, they have equally contributed to the study conception, design, data collection, analyses, interpretation of results and the preparation of the manuscript draft, review results and the approval of the last version.

REFERENCES

- [1] <https://wallstreetwindow.com/five-problem-of-bureaucracy>
- [2] <https://wallstreetwindow.com/five-problem-of-bureaucracy>
- [3] Mohammed, Tibek and Endot. (2013). The impact of Bureaucracy on Strategic Decisions-Making Process in The Islamic Call Society. *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 7(2), pp.529-534. <https://pdf4pro.com/amp/view/the-impact-of-bureaucracy-on-strategic-decision-11420c.html>
- [4] Chipea F. & Banciu, V. (2013) Bureaucracy versus New Administrative management. Available at <http://socioumane.ro/blog/analesocioumane/2013/10/01-Bureaucracy--versus-new-administrative-management>. Pdf. Accessed on May 25, 2016. [Chickpea F.& Banciu, V. \(2013\) Bureaucracy versus New Administrative management. Available at http://socioumane.ro/blog/analesocioumane/2013/10/01-Bureaucracy--versus-new-administrative-management. Pdf. Accessed on May 25, 2016.](http://socioumane.ro/blog/analesocioumane/2013/10/01-Bureaucracy--versus-new-administrative-management)
- [5] Hamel, G. (2006), The why, What, and How of Management Innovation. *Harvard Business Review*, pp.72-84. <https://hbr.org/2006/02/the-why-what-and-how-of-management-innovation>
- [6] Steiber, A., (2014), The Google Model. Managing Continuous Innovation in a Rapidly Changing World. Springer. <https://www.scribd.com/book/576597218/The-Google-Model-Managing-Continuous-Innovation-in-a-Rapidly-Changing-World>
- [7] Azizi Senkukul & Behrooz Gharlegghi, (2025). Factors Influencing Foreign Direct Investment Inflow in Tanzania. *International Journal of Business and Management*, Vol.10, No.7
- [8] Larbi, G.A, (2003), United Nations Research Institute for Development. Discussion paper 112.
- [9] Ref: <https://www.thoughtco.com/bureaucracy-definition-examples-pros-cons-4580229>
- [10] Wilson Woodrow, (2010) " The Study of Administration." *Political Science Quarterly*, Vol.2, No.2, JSTOR, December 29. <https://faculty.fiu.edu/~revellk/pad3003/Wilson.pdf>
- [11] Weber, Max. 'Economy and Society.' Volume 1, Guenther Roth (Editor), Claus Wittich (Editor), First Edition, University of California Press, October 2013).
- [12] Mohammed, Tibek and Endot. (2013). The impact of Bureaucracy on Strategic Decisions-Making Process in The Islamic Call Society. *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 7(2), pp.529-534. <https://pdf4pro.com/amp/view/the-impact-of-bureaucracy-on-strategic-decision-11420c.html>
- [13] Dobrescu, M., Hristache, D., Lacob, S. (2012), " Recent Theoretical Progress in Economics and its impact on Economic Policy", *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences Journal*, Elsevier, The World Conference on Business, Economics and Management (BEM-2012), Antalya, Turkey. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/257716506_Recent_Theoretical_Progress_in_Economics_and_Its_Impact_on_Economic_Policy
- [14] Laurentiu Gabriel, (2014). The effects of Bureaucracy over the business environment from Romania, *Theoretical and Applied Economics*. Volume XXI (2014), No.2(591), pp 115-125. <http://store.ectap.ro/articole/958.pdf>

- [15] Mahiti, F.M. (2012). *Determinants of Foreign Direct Investment in East Africa Countries of Tanzania and Kenya*. Master Thesis, Mzumbe University. <https://docplayer.net/41422994-Determinants-of-foreign-direct-investments-fdis-in-east-africa-countries-of-tanzania-and-kenya.html>
- [16] Charles. Domician, (2008). How Does Sectoral FDI Enhance Export Earnings? The Tanzania Experience, Tanzania Trade Experts' Association. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/323174996_Does_Sectoral_FDI_Enhance_Export_Earnings_The_Tanzania_Experiences#fullTextFileContent
- [17] Bahrulmazi, B, E., Gharleghi, B., B., Benjamin, C.Y.F., & Tan, M. (2014). Critical Success Factors Affecting Malaysia' SMEs through Inward FDI: Case of Service Sector. *Asian Social Sciences*, 10 (16), 131-138. <http://dx.doi.org./10.5539/ass.v10n16p131>
- [18] Maria Mikazda and Shaddin Alhajahmad, (2018). Investment and Business in Jordan to Create Employment Opportunities and Challenges. Published by the WANA Institute, Royal Scientific Society in Amman, Jordan. http://wanainstitute.org/sites/default/files/publications/Publication_InvestmentAndBusinessJordan_English.pdf
- [19] Landstrom. H. (2005). "Pioneers in entrepreneurship and small business research": Springer Science and Business Media, Inc. Boston. https://www.academia.edu/27172038/Pioneers_in_Entrepreneurship_Research
- [20] <https://wallstreetwindow.com/five-problem-of-bureaucracy>
- [21] Moynihan, D., Pandey, S., and Wright, B. (2011). Setting the Table: How Transformational Leadership Fosters Performance Information Use. *Journal of public Administration Research and Thorny*, JPART 22: 143-164. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228465118_Setting_the_Table_How_Transformational_Leadership_Fosters_Performance_Information_Use
- [22] Hsu, C., Marsh, and Mannari, H. (1983). An Examination of the Determinants of Organizational Structure. *American Journal of Sociology*, Vol.88, No 5, pp975-996 <https://www.journals.uchicago.edu/doi/10.1086/227766>
- [23] Organ, Dennis and Greene, Charles. (1983),the effects of Formalization on Professional Involvement: A Compensatory Process Approach. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, Vol. 26, No. 2, pp. 237-252
- [24] Armandi, B., and Jr. E. (1985). Bureaucratic and Personalizes Strategies for Efficiency and Organization: An Investigation of Structure and Efficiency in a Set of 104 Profit- Seeking Firms. *American Journal of Economical and Sociology*, Vol.44, No.3, pp.261-277
- [25] Jaskyte, Kristina. (2011). Predictors of Administrative and Ethnological Innovations in Nonprofit Organizations. *Public Administration Review*, Vol. 71, No.1, pp.77-87
- [26] Magnini, B., Not. E., Stock, O., Strapparava, C. (2000). "Natural language processing for transparent communication between public administration and citizens", Artificial Intelligence and law, *Khwer Academic Publishers*
- [27] UK Essays. (November 2018). Why Companies Lose Competitive Advantages Marketing Essays. <https://www.ukessays.com/essays/marketing/why-companies-lose-competitive-advantages-marketing-essay.php?vref=1>
- [28] <https://wallstreetwindow.com/five-problem-of-bureaucracy>

- [29] <https://www.managementstudyhq.com/advantages-and-disadvantages-of-bureaucracy.html>
- [30] Wilson, Woodrow. (2010). "The Study of Administration." *Political Science Quarterly*, December 29, Vol.2, No.2, JSTOR.
- [31] Adamolekun, Public administration in Africa. Colorado: Westview Press: 1999.
- [32] Igbo;we-Ibeto CJ. (2020). Analyzing the interface between bureaucracy, interest groups, and public policymaking for good governance in Africa. *International Journal of Business Management Studies*.12 (2):273-288.
https://sobiad.org/eJOURNALS/journal_IJBM/archives/IJBM_2020-2/c-j-Igbokwe-Ibeto.pdf
- [33] <https://rise8.us/thoughts/overcoming-the-5-main-problems-of-bureaucracy/>
- [34] <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/c/corruption.asp>.
- [35] Hamel, G. (2012) For Innovation to Flourish in Your Organization, "Bureaucracy Must Die".
From <http://www.Industryweek.com/global-economy/innovation-flourish-your-organization-bureaucracy-must-die>. Accessed on May 27, 2016.
- [36] <https://wallstreetwindow.com/five-problem-of-bureaucracy>
- [37]. Monteiro, Pedro, and Paul S. (2022) Adler. "Bureaucracy for the 21st century: Clarifying and expanding our view of bureaucratic organization." *Academy of Management Annals* 16, no. 2: 427-475.
https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=4008916
- [38] Timothy Besley,¹ Robin Burgess,¹ Adnan Khan,¹ and Guo Xu² (2022). *IJPSM* 36,2, Vol. 14:397-424. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-economics-080521-011950>
<https://www.emerald.com/insight/0951-3558.htm>
- [39] Tesa lea, (2021). "Desiring Bureaucracy" *Annual Review of Anthropology*, 50: pp59-74.
<https://www.annualreviews.org/doi/10.1146/annurev-anthro-101819-110147>
- [40] Andre Vaz, Lopes and Diego, Mota, Vieira. (2022). "Between politics and bureaucracy: a systematic literature review on the dynamics of public appointments" *IJPSM* 36, 2: 152-170.
<https://www.emerald.com/insight/0951-3558.htm>
- [41] Chelsa Jordan, (2019). "Libraries as bureaucracies: a SWOT analysis" *Library Management*, vol 40. No.5, pp: 294-304. www.emeraldinsight.com/0143-5124.htm
- [42] Saunders., Lewis. and Thorn hill, A. (2003). *Research methods for business students* (3rd Ed) Harlow, England: Financial Times Prentice Hall.
- [43] Raosoft (2004), Raosoft Sample Size Calculator, Retrieved from internet on 29 February 2019, and http://www.Rasoft.com/sample_size.html
- [44] Cooper, R.D., and Shindler, S.P. (2007). *Business research methods*, (9th Ed). New York: McGraw-Hill.
- [45] Hair, J.F., Anderson, R.E., Tatham, R.L., & Black, W.C. (2010). *Multivariate Data Analysis*, Pearson Education, Upper Saddle River, NJ
- [46] Yousef Ishak and Ismail, Ramah (2002), "Human Resources Competiveness and Inflow of Foreign Direct investment on ASEAN Region", *Asia – Pacific Development Journal* Vol.9, No.1, June 2002
- [47] Dobrescu, M., Hristache, D., Iacob, S. (2012). "Recent theoretical progress in economic and its impact on economic policy". *Procedia Social and Behavioral Sciences Journal*, Elsevier. The word Conference on Business, Economics and Management (BEM-2012), Antalya, Turkey.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/257716506_Recent_Theoretical_Progress_in_Economics_and_Its_Impact_on_Economic_Policy

[48] Cruz C, Keefer P. (2015). Political Parties, Clientelism, bureaucratic reform *Comp. Polit. Studies.* 48: 1942-73. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0010414015594627>

[49] Larbi, G.A., (2003), United Nations Research Institute for Social development, Discussion Paper 112. <https://docplayer.net/11583612-Source-larbi-g-a-united-nations-research-institute-for-social-development-discussion-paper-112-1999-updated-2003.html>